

Data4Cit SciNews

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CHANGE

Credits

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CONTENTS

- 4 Foreword
- 8 Invited essay
- 14 Installations

FORE

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Data does not always provide neutral and straightforward representations of the world, but is rather entangled with politics and culture, money and power. Citizen science journalism is an emerging field where citizen science (i.e. a methodology where new knowledge is created with the contribution of society, either as data collectors, with the help of low tech sensors, contributing to data analysis or acting as co-researchers) and data journalism come together.

Cooperating in the definition of citizens' information needs and designing proper sets of data collection in a participatory and transparent way can contribute to the use of those data to empower change for the benefit of local communities and advocate for democracy.

DATA4CitSciNEWS exhibition showcases interactive installations, co-creation processes and investigative methods that open up a discussion on how citizens and journalists can come together to tackle current needs, in an era marked by the rise and spread of misinformation, disinformation and fake news. Case-studies published in press and film screenings also intend to explore the potential of visual and storytelling narratives of citizen science and data journalism as well as principles for quality science journalism to raise awareness and bridge the gap between science and society.

During the itinerant DATA4CitSciNEWS exhibition we will be asking visitors to contribute to the definition of the emerging “citizen science journalism”, expressing their thoughts on different aspects such as how citizens can contribute to journalism. So far, we have had a positive response and found the will of activating their voices by “inviting each other; telling stories; sharing experiences; helping to shape it; by crowdsourcing or collecting data; contributing as active players in the investigation”. By opening the dialogue, in the eyes of the visitors, citizen science journalism should be radically inclusive, an independent source of knowledge about society, collaborative, rigorous, contributive and open. Moreover, priority topics of concern are being found to be those related with health and mental illness, food systems, circular economy and sustainability, air and odour pollution, social issues, neighborhood life and inclusiveness.

Hoping that amplifying these voices can have a positive effect in building a new model for better connected and integrated science communication and journalism with social impact that can also benefit the knowledge production process itself.

Joana Magalhães, Curator
and Senior Researcher at SfC

INVITED

ESSAY

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Makoko, a water-front settlement in the centre of Lagos, Nigeria, is estimated to be home to around 250,000 people, most of whom live in difficult conditions. Despite being only a few kilometers away from the financial center of the city, not far from the oil and gas companies' headquarters in Victoria Island, the place used to be a blank spot on the map until recently.

A team at Code for Africa, a non-profit organisation working on civic technology and digital transformation in African countries, and its partners worked with the local community to create a bottom-up, open source map of the area using drones, smartphones, and crowdsourcing. Putting themselves on the map was a way for the community to state their right to exist.

The mapping project was captured in a flagship story produced by international media partners and is meant to be an ongoing process. In 2020 the project team returned to Makoko and conducted fresh water samples for analysis, mapping a further 20 clean water sources as POIs in Makoko.

Makoko: The Venice of Africa
Errol Barnett
CNN

Mapping Makoko Using Drones and Canoes

In 2021 two Nigerian medical researchers Dr Ayesha Akinkugbe from Lagos University Teaching Hospital and College of Medicine, University of Lagos and Dr Obianuju Ozoh from The Lagos University Teaching Hospital, in collaboration with Code for Africa's Knowledge team, conducted scientific research on the ground. The research was to determine the enablers and barriers to the Covid-19 vaccine uptake in the Makoko informal settlement in Nigeria.

Organising interventions in Makoko on public health in a place where hundreds of thousands of people live without a map would

be almost impossible. In a case like the COVID-19 pandemic or other epidemics, the map can be used as a tool by international organisations and also by the local government to organise support and distribute resources to the community, as proven by the University of Lagos (UNILAG) medical researchers who leveraged the Makoko's open data and citizen science effort to conduct field research.

The partnership with UNILAG is particular remarkable and shows how a development project such as MapMakoko can leverage citizen science and feed into academic research.

In the case of MapMakoko, citizen science is evident in the involvement of the local population in the mapping process. The training and mapping sessions had an impact on the scientific literacy of the population in multiple ways.

Citizen science refers to the participation of members of the public in scientific research, either by collecting data or by contributing to scientific studies. In the case of MapMakoko, citizen science is evident in the involvement of the local population in the mapping process. The training sessions and mapping sessions had an impact on the scientific literacy of the population in multiple ways. Firstly, by training the local population to use digital tools and drones to create the map, they were given the opportunity to develop skills that are relevant to scientific research. They learned about geospatial technology, mapping techniques, and data analysis. These skills are not only relevant to mapping a slum but are also transferable to other scientific fields. By gaining these skills, the local population is better equipped to participate in future scientific research projects.

Secondly, the involvement of the local population in the mapping process had a broader impact on scientific literacy in the community. By participating in the project, they were given the opportunity to learn about the importance of data and evidence-based decision making. They also gained an understanding of how scientific research can be used to address real-world problems and improve people's lives. This understanding of the value of scientific research can help to increase support for future scientific endeavors in the community.

This proves **how a crowdsourced map can help propel academic research and proposes a new way of involving marginalised communities in scientific projects.**

Jacopo Ottaviani,
Journalist and
computer scientist

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Citizen Science Journalism Cloud

Citizen science journalism aims to contribute to the use of citizen-generated data to empower change for the benefit of local communities and advocate for democracy. As a citizen, what are the most important values citizen science journalism should respect? Through a QR code, visitors are able to share the most important values that should be at the core of this new concept.

Credits: Science for Change
Background Image: Cities at Night

Citizen Science Journalism under construction

In this interactive piece, visitors are invited to co-create a definition of citizen science journalism. Which data, whose data and by which means? Who has the capacity to benefit from it? How can journalists be able to report on reality in a much deeper and meaningful way to benefit citizens and communities?

This will feed into an ongoing research spurred by the NEWSERA project, fostering a common place where citizen science and data journalism come together.

Credits : Science for Change

Beyond PSIs

The priority of communication and scientific journalism is to respond to the needs of society and allow the public to fully exercise their rights as citizens. Principles, Standards and Indicators (PSI) must be at the center of a solid ethical and deontological approach to scientific communication and journalism. The principles are fundamental truths to guide scientific communication and journalism; a set of standards should respond to each principle as general recommendations; and finally, the indicators are a practical way to measure and monitor the path towards the successful use of the principles and standards. Throughout 8 panels, the different PSIs are explored, also inviting visitors to reflect on possible PSIs from the perspective of the new concept of citizen scientific journalism.

Credits : Science for Change
PSIs obtained in participatory sessions under the ENJOI project

How Makoko was connected to the digital world map

Mapping Makoko is a project mapping the informal settlements in Nigeria. The open data map is published in an open street map and created with the engagement of locals. A project that aims to the transfer of knowledge about data and to create a relationship with local media.

Credits: Code for Africa, AfricanDRONE, GuardianNG

Mapping Light Pollution

Cities at Night is a citizen science project to catalog, locate and geo reference night photos taken from the International Space Station. The project is for the first time, building a map of night sky images obtained from satellites orbiting the Earth, entirely in real colour, using pictures with up to 150 times more resolution than the images used to build the Black Marble Map. These images are a very useful tool to detect excessive lighting and where light should be improved. Furthermore, the archives of images taken during recent years allow to study the evolution of light pollution and can have a significant impact on future policies related to the effects of light pollution in human health, biodiversity, etc.

Credits : Science for Change
 Images : Cities at Night

Citizen Science Journalism: the NEWSERA Pilots

In order to test the developing concept of Citizen Science Journalism and find ways to bring citizen science projects together with data journalists, NEWSERA launched a pairing activity among journalists and selected Pilots. This allows one to better understand the process of writing and publishing a piece of journalism based on CS-generated data. Hereby several publications that came out of NEWSERA Pilots in international media are shown.

Credits: Science for Change
 Adapted from original articles by: Marco Boscolo and Antonio Massariolo, for Il Bo Live (IT), Storydata for Diari de Barcelona (ES), Claudia Carvalho Silva, Cátia Mendonça, José Alves and Francisco Lopes, for Público (PT); translation and text adaptation: Elisabetha Tola, Clara Civit and Joana Magalhães.

If toxic air is a monument to slavery, how do we take it down?

Along the Mississippi River, lies a region once called 'Plantation Country', now known as the 'Petrochemical Corridor'. Over 200 industrial plants occupy the fallow footprints of formerly slave-powered sugarcane plantations. In the shadow of those plants, neighboring communities breathe some of the most toxic air in the US. As industry poisons their air, it crushes the remains of their ancestors.

Across the ruined mosaic of plantations, hundreds of Black cemeteries face desecration by frenzied development. This film clearly reveals the interlink between toxicity in post-plantation landscapes with environmental racism, based on research.

Credits: Forensic Architecture in partnership with RISE St. James

History of Information Graphics

From cosmic charts and da Vinci's Vitruvian Man to the New York subway map: trace the history of visual data from the Middle Ages to the digital era in this XL compendium. Featuring some 400 infographic milestones across technology, cartography, zoology, and more, this is an unprecedented reference work for designers, history buffs, and anyone thirsty for knowledge.

Credits: TASCHEN

